

“AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE AND THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF MADATYAYA(ALCOHOLISM): A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW”

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ABSTRACT

Madatyaya (alcoholism) is a major socio-economic and health problem that affects not only individuals but also their families and society at large. It is a disorder caused by improper and excessive consumption of alcohol over a prolonged period, which may lead to dependence and withdrawal symptoms. In Ayurveda, Madatyaya is described as a Tridoshaja Vyadhi resulting from faulty intake of Madya, which vitiates Agni, Ojas, and Manas. According to classical texts, alcohol acts as nectar when consumed properly but behaves like poison when misused. The Ayurvedic management of Madatyaya primarily includes Shodhana (purificatory therapies), Shamana (palliative treatment), Rasayana (rejuvenation therapy), and Satvavajaya Chikitsa (psychotherapy). Several recent clinical studies have explored the role of Panchakarma procedures, internal medications, and Medhya-Rasayana drugs in the management

of Madatyaya and withdrawal symptoms. This review attempts to compile and analyze available classical references and recent research studies to highlight effective Ayurvedic treatment modalities in the management of Madatyaya.

KEYWORDS: Madatyaya, Alcoholism, Panchakarma, Ayurveda, Recent treatment approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol consumption is a global public health concern, contributing significantly to physical illness, mental disorders, social disruption, and economic burden. Chronic and excessive intake of alcohol leads to dependence and withdrawal syndromes, affecting multiple organ systems, particularly the liver, nervous system, and mental health.

In Ayurveda, Madatyaya is described in detail in Charaka Samhita as a disease caused by improper and excessive intake of Madya. According to Acharya Charaka, after ingestion, Madya reaches the Hridaya (heart) and afflicts its ten Gunas, resulting in agitation of the mind and loss of normal mental functions. The Hridaya is the seat of Rasa circulation, Indriya, Buddhi, Atma, and Ojas; therefore, excessive alcohol intake leads to impairment of immunity, intellect, sensory functions, and mental stability.

Three stages of intoxication are described in the classics. In the first stage, Ojas is not significantly affected, though mental excitation occurs. In the second stage, Ojas is moderately disturbed. In the final stage, Ojas is severely afflicted, resulting in serious systemic and psychological manifestations. Based on Dosha predominance, Madatyaya is classified into Vataja, Pittaja, Kaphaja, and Sannipataja types. Among these, Sannipataja Madatyaya is considered the most severe, as all three Doshas are involved and Madya acts similar to Visha (poison), potentially leading to fatal outcomes.

Ayurveda emphasizes that Madya acts as Amrita when consumed judiciously according to prescribed rules, but becomes Visha when taken excessively and improperly. Hence, the treatment of Madatyaya requires a holistic approach aimed at correcting Dosha imbalance, restoring Agni, protecting Ojas, and stabilizing mental functions.

In recent years, several clinical studies have explored the effectiveness of Panchakarma therapies such as Vamana and Basti, along with Shamana and Rasayana drugs, in the management of Madatyaya and its withdrawal symptoms. This review attempts to compile and critically analyze such classical and contemporary research works to understand their therapeutic relevance in the management of Madatyaya.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To scientifically evaluate various articles and identify various unique treatment aspects followed in the management of Madatyaya.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Various sources like classical Ayurvedic books, medical literature, research updates, scientific publications, online articles and websites were consulted and examined to explore various treatment aspects of Madatyaya.

DISCUSSION

Madya considered as one of the Ahara Dravya and acts as nectar when taken properly following the rules and regulations, otherwise it acts like a poison. An attempt has been done to collaborate various research articles to have effective management of madatyaya.

An attempt was made with innovative combination of basti. Dhanyakahimabasti comprises Dhanyakahima as Kwatha, Kalyanakaghrita 10 as Sneha Dravya, Yastimadhu (Glycyrrhiza glabra), Musta (Cyperus rotundus), Brahmi (Bacopa monnieri) as Kalka along with, Makshika (~Honey) and Lavana (Salt) in modified Yoga basti schedule with Niruhabasti in the morning and Anuvasanabasti with Kalyanka ghrita10 in the afternoon. The Dhanyakahima⁸ possesses properties like Tikta, Katu rasa, Tridoshanasak, Trishnanashaka (~decrease the thirst), Dahanasak (~Reduced the burning sensation), Jwara (~Fever), Deepana-pachana (~Increases metabolism), Sodhana (~Purification) effect. Yasthimadhu, Bramhi, Musta churna as kalkadravya10gm each, Musta (Cyperus rotundus) having tikta, katu, kasaya rasa, kaphapitta hara property, and Bramhi (Bacopa monnieri) having tikta rasa prominent vatapitta hara property.

Sadyovamana to the patient on the first day with Saindhavajala and Yastimadhu Phanta. Bahirparimarjana Chikitsa, which is performed in Pratilomagatias Bahya Rookshana karma its effected kapha & Vata disorder by causing liquefaction of kapha & Meda, promotes the metabolism. Takradhara with Amlaki(Emibilica officinale) & Jatamansi (Nardostacyesjatamandsi) and Musta (Cyperus rotundus) powder, in Takradhara aids in Raktgatavata (~Increase the blood pressure), Anidra (Insomnia), Avasada, Vatapittaja disorder, Ojakshaya (~ Low immunity), Smriti Nasa (~Loss of memory). Kalyanaka ghrita10 was prescribed for Shamanga Snehapana and also in Basti, Tridosahara gunas are present in Haritaki, Vibhitaki, Amla, Vishala, Sariva, and Kalayanaka ghrita10 is indicated in Meha, Moha, Gara Visha, Monovyadha, Buddhinasa, Smriti, and Ayushya. Manasmrita Manasa 14 Mitra vati is indicated in the Sarva Manodosha Hara, Buddhi, Unmada Nasaka so this was prescribed. Guda & Brita helps to improve sleep by showing effects on balancing the Vata dosha and increases Kapha dosha, guda, ghrita combination is vatapittahara and sheetavirya

and kapha karaka. The combination contains Madhura rasa and helps to improve sleep by kaphavardhakaaction.^[2]

Shrikandasava a Shamana Yoga in Madatyaya with main ingredient as Shrikanda which is popularly known as Chandana. According to classical reference, it is said that Shrikhanda is Kaphapitta Shamaka, which is indicated in Daha, Ati Svedajanya Dourgandhya, Manasikavyagrata, Dourbalya, Trisna, Amlapitta, Kamala, Hriddorbalya, Visha which are found in Madatyaya also and Shrikhanda due to its Katu Vipaka pacifies Vata and Kapha, its Sheeta Guna acts against Ushna and Teekshna Guna of Pitta. Maricha is Kaphavatahara, Medohara, stimulant and tonic for nerves, remedy in liver dysfunction. Jatamamsi is Tridosahara, mainly indicated in Nidranasha, Agnimandya, Kampavata and has anti-anxiety action. Haridra has properties such as Raktaprasadana, Tridoshashamaka, anti-hepatotoxic and CNS depressant. Tagara is Kapha-Vatahara, Rasayana, tranquilizer and nervine, Pippali is Kaphavatahara, anti giardial immune stimulatory, hepatoprotective. All the drugs collectively act as Tridosahara and based on their chemical composition they act on CNS and other systems to provide relief from the Madatyaya condition.

Amapachana with Shunti Churna one tea spoon thrice a day with hot water before food for 2 days, then Snehapana with Moorchita Ghrita till the samyak snigdha lakshana, followed by Abhyanga with Moorchita Taila, and during Vishrama Kala patient was advised to take Kaphakara Ahara. Then Vamana was administered with Madanaphala Yoga. Then Shuddhi Tarpanadi Samsarjana Krama was advised for 3-7 days. Then Astanga Lavana in the dose of half Karsha (6 gm) twice a day, before food was given for the period of 1month. During treatment period patient was asked to report once in 8 days and during follow up period once in 15 days for 2 months. The subjective and objective criteria were assessed before and after the treatment. Second group was given Placebo capsules in the dose of 1 capsule twice a day for the period of 1 month in place of Astanga Lavana after Vamana of first group, rest of the treatment was same in both groups.

As Madatyaya is Kahapradhana Vyadhi with Agnidusti, so the drug which is beneficial in treating both Agni as well as kapha Dosha is the better choice in the management of Madatyaya. Astanga Lavana is one among those which mainly acts as Deepana, Pachaka and Kaphahara. The ingredients are Souvarchala (Unaqua Sodie Chloridum) It is prepared from Sarjaakshaara and Saamudra Lavaṇa by Lavaṇa Kalpana process. It is Rocaka, Deepana, Pachaka, Vaatahara, Udgarashuddhikara and Anahahara. Ajaji (Cuminum cyminum Linn), It

contains one type of volatile oil in quantity of 2-4% which gives smell and taste, other contents are 20-40% cumaldehyde, protein 18.7%, carbohydrate 26.6%, fiber 12%, minerals 4.8%, calcium 1.08%, phosphorus 0.49%, iron 31 mg/100 gm; Vit A 870 I.U., Vit C 3 mg /100 gm Vrukshaamla (*Garcinia indica* Chois), Fruit contains citric acid. Amlavetasa (*Garcinia pedunculata* Roxb), and this study showed It contains mainly 13-20% Malic acid. Twak (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), It contains 50-65% cinnamaldehyde and 60-75% eugenol. Ela (*Elettaria cardamomum* Maton), Volatile oils 2-8%, potassium salt 3%, starch 3%, ash 6-10%. In taila main contents are cineol, terpineol, terpinene, limonene and sabinene Mareecha (*Piper nigrum* Linn), It contains piperine 5-10%, piperidine 5%, pipretine and chavicine. Volatile oils 1–2.6%, fiber 14.6%, fats 7%, protein 11.55%, carbohydrate 41.6%, minerals 4.4%, calcium 460mg, phosphorus 198 mg, iron 16.8 mg, thiamin 0.06 mg, riboflavin 0.14 mg, nicotinic acid 1.4 mg in every 100 gm and vit. A 1800 I.U. The chemical analysis of Astanga Lavana was done at shreedhareeyam Ayurvedic Medicine (p) Ltd on 01/10/08 which revealed Sodium Bicarbonate – 13.25% Hydroxyl citric acid – 17.66 % Piperine – 1.266 – Zingerol – 3.11.^[3]

Administration of Madhya (Madhya Prayoga)

Intake of excessive alcohol which is Tikshna (sharp), hot, sour and Vidahi (causing burning sensation) makes the anna-rasa (juice of food after digestion) sticky and improperly digested (vidagdha) which ultimately turns alkaline (kshara) and causes antardaha (burning sensation in the interior of the body), fever, morbid thirst, unconsciousness, giddiness and intoxication instantaneously. To correct these ailments, alcohol should be administered when an alkaline substance (kshara) gets mixed up with a sour substance, the outcome becomes sweet in taste and alcohol is best among the articles having sour taste.^[4]

A study was conducted over Punarnavadi Ghritta which contains maximum 8 parts of Punarnava which is very effective in treatment of stress, inflammation, diabetes, nephrotic syndrome and also possess anti-inflammatory, diuretic and immunomodulatory activities. Yastimadhu, go-dugdha, go-ghrita have Tridosha shamaka effect and increase Oja, Bala, Dhatu by its Brimhana and Rasayana effects. Which helps in removing toxins from the body, act as liver stimulant, brain tonic, ojavardhaka, balya, dhatuvaradhaka.^[5]

CONCLUSION

Madatyaya (alcoholism) is a complex psychosomatic disorder affecting both the body and mind, with serious social and familial consequences. Ayurveda describes Madatyaya as a

Tridoshaja Vyadhi caused by improper and excessive intake of Madya, leading to derangement of Agni, Ojas, and Manas. Classical texts emphasize that Madya acts like nectar when consumed judiciously but behaves as poison when misused.

This review highlights that the management of Madatyaya should be comprehensive and individualized, focusing on Shodhana, Shamana, Rasayana, and Satvavajaya Chikitsa. Various clinical studies reviewed in this article demonstrate the effectiveness of Panchakarma procedures such as Vamana and Basti, along with internal medications like Kalyanaka Ghrita, Astanga Lavana, Shrikhandasava, and Punarnavadi Ghrita. These therapies act by correcting Agnidushti, pacifying Tridosha, strengthening Ojas, improving hepatic function, and stabilizing mental faculties.

Innovative approaches such as Dhanyaka Hima Basti, Takradhara, and the use of medhya and rasayana drugs show promising results in reducing withdrawal symptoms, improving sleep, cognition, and overall quality of life in patients of Madatyaya. The multimodal Ayurvedic approach not only addresses physical detoxification but also provides psychological support and rejuvenation.

Thus, Ayurveda offers a holistic and scientifically relevant framework for the management of Madatyaya. Integrating classical principles with evidence-based clinical research can provide a safe, effective, and sustainable treatment strategy for alcoholism and its associated complications.

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